

FORMULATION & DEVELOPMENT OF ANTIPSORIATIC GEL FOR TOPICAL DRUG DELIVERY

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ABSTRACT

- FTIR spectroscopy studies confirmed that there is compatibility between drug and excipients.
- Gel was prepared by using Dimethyl sulfoxide, Carbopol 10NF, propylene glycol, glycerol, methyl paraben, propyl paraben and water.
- The Optimized formulation (F3) is more effective compared to all formulations.
- The Prepared Gel showed acceptable Physical properties such as pH (4.99), assay (100.9%w/w) And In vitro diffusion studies have shown 98.2% drug release in 48 hours.
- Formulation was loaded for stability at Accelerated condition 40°C/75%RH and 30°C/65%RH for 1,2 and 3 month. Optimized formulation (F3) has shown good stability and acceptable In vitro performance.

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Skin

1.1.1. Structure of skin^[1]

The human skin is a multilayered organ composed of many histological layers. Skin is the most accessible organ in the body. The skin of an average adult body covers an approximate surface area of two square meters and receives about one-third of the blood circulating through the body. Skin is the complex organ and allows the passage of various chemicals into and across the skin. Skin serves as the point of administration for a few systemically active

drugs, the drug applied topically will be absorbed, first into the systemic circulation and then transported to target tissues. It is the largest organ in the body and has a surface area of about 1.5-2m² in adults and it contains glands, hair and nails.

a) Epidermis^[2]

The epidermis is the outer layer of the skin, defined as a stratified squamous epithelium, primarily comprising keratinocytes in progressive stages of differentiation. Keratinocytes produce the protein keratin and are the major building blocks (cells) of the epidermis. As the epidermis is avascular (contains no blood vessels), it is entirely dependent on the underlying dermis for nutrient delivery and waste disposal through the basement membrane. The prime function of the epidermis is to act as a physical and biological barrier to the external environment, preventing penetration by irritants and allergens. At the same time, it prevents the loss of water and maintains internal homeostasis. The epidermis is composed of layers; most body parts have four layers, but those with the thickest skin have five.

The layers are:

1. Stratum corneum (horny layer).
2. Stratum lucidum (only found in thick skin – that is, the palms of the hands, the soles of the feet and the digits).
3. Stratum granulosum (granular layer).
4. Stratum spinosum (prickle cell layer).
5. Stratum basale (germinative layer).
6. The epidermis also contains other cell structures. Keratinocytes make up around 95% of the epidermal cell population – the others being melanocytes, Langerhans cells and Merkel cells.

b) Dermis

The dermis is tough and elastic. It is formed from connective tissue and the matrix contains collagen fibers interlaced with elastic fibers. The rupture of these elastic fibers may occur when the skin is overstretched which results in permanent striae, or stretch marks that is commonly found in pregnancy and obesity. Collagen fibers bind with water to give tensile strength to the skin which decreases with age and hence wrinkles appear. Fibroblasts, macrophages and mast cells are the main cells found in the dermis. Under its deepest layers are the areolar tissue and varying amounts of adipose (fat) tissue.

The structures in the dermis are

- Blood Vessels
- Lymph Vessels
- Sensory Nerve Endings
- Sweat Glands
- Hairs
- Arrector pili muscles and
- Sebaceous glands.

1.1.2. Mechanisms of skin penetration^[3]

There are various ways by which molecules can cross the stratum corneum, they are:

- Intercellular route
- Transcellular route and
- Appendageal route (through either sweat gland or hair follicle)

Under normal circumstances Appendageal route is not to be very significant, in part this is due to the low surface area occupied by the appendages. It is difficult to determine the differences between the transcellular and intercellular routes. Research work, *in-vivo*, on the skin absorption of methyl nicotinate was analyzed using solutions to Fick's law of diffusion and the best fit to the data was found for a diffusional path length of 350nm. Since the thickness of the skin is approximately 1/20

1.2. Topical Drug Delivery^[4]

Drug molecules with low doses can be delivered through topical route effectively that are limited to a small area anywhere in the body. Stratum corneum is lipid-rich in nature and it is composed of 40% of lipids, 40% of protein, and only 20% of water. Lipophilic nature of the drug is best suited for topical delivery whose transport is aided by dissolution into intercellular lipids around the cells of the stratum corneum. However, the drugs which are hydrophilic in nature are difficult to transport to the stratum corneum layer because of its low water content.

These molecules are absorbed into the skin through pores or openings of the hair follicles and sebaceous glands that restricts drug absorption. Percutaneous absorption is an ideal factor considered in topical drug delivery systems in order to achieve and maintain a uniform, systemic, therapeutic levels throughout the duration of use. The drug delivered passively via

skin should have adequate lipophilicity and a molecular weight of less than 500 Da. Drugs applied via dermally reaches the area in optimum concentration by reducing the side effects and by increasing bioavailability and patient compliance

1.2.1. Rationale for topical preparation

With the purpose to formulate an efficient and effective topical preparation, considerations are mainly concerned with the site of action of the drugs and its effect.

1.3. Gels^[5]

The term 'Gel' was introduced in the late 1800 to name some semisolid material according to their physiological characteristics rather than molecular composition The U.S.P. defines gels as a semisolid system consisting of dispersion made up of either small inorganic particle or large organic molecule enclosing and interpenetrated by liquid. Gels are a substantially dilute cross-linked system, which exhibits no flow when in the steady-state. They consist of a two component semi-solid system rich in liquid. Their one characteristic feature is the presence of continuous structure providing solid like properties. Gels have become a premier materials used for drug delivery formulations due to its biocompatibility, network structure and molecular stability of the incorporated bioactive agent.

1.3.1. STRUCTURE OF GELS

A gel consists of a natural or synthetic polymer forming a three dimensional matrix throughout a dispersion medium or hydrophilic liquid. After application, the liquid evaporates leaving the drug entrapped in a thin film of the gel – forming matrix physically covering the skin. The presence of a network formed by the interlocking of particles of the gelling agent gives rise to the rigidity of a gel. The nature of the particles and the type of form that is responsible for the linkages determine the structure of the network and the property of the gel.

1.3.2. CHARACTERISTICS OF GELS

Gels should possess the following properties

- Ideally, the gelling agent for pharmaceutical or cosmetic use should be inert, safe, and should not react with other formulation components.
- The gelling agent included in the preparation should produce a reasonable solid-like nature during storage that can be easily broken when subjected to shear forces generated by shaking the bottle, squeezing the tube, or during topical application.
- It should possess suitable anti-microbial activity against microbial attack.

- The topical gel should not be tacky.
- The gels intended for ophthalmic use should be sterile.

A. Swelling

When a gelling agent is kept in contact with liquid that solvates it, then an appreciable amount of liquid is taken up by the agent and the volume increases. This process is referred to as swelling. This phenomenon occurs as the solvent penetrates the matrix. Gel-gel interactions are replaced by gel solvent interactions. The degree of swelling depends on the number of linkages between individual molecules of gelling agent and on the strength of these linkages.

B. Syneresis

Many gels often contract spontaneously on standing and exude some fluid medium. This effect is known as syneresis. The degree to which syneresis occurs, increases as the concentration of gelling agent decreases. The occurrence of syneresis indicates that the original gel was thermodynamically unstable. The mechanism of contraction has been related to the relaxation of elastic stress developed during the setting of the gels. As these stresses are relieved, the interstitial space available for the solvent is reduced, forcing the liquid out.

C. Ageing

Colloidal systems usually exhibit slow spontaneous aggregation. This process is referred to as ageing. In gels, ageing results in gradual formation of a denser network of the gelling agent. In gels, ageing results in gradual formation of a denser network of the gelling agent. Theimer suggests that this process is similar to the original gelling process and continues after the initial gelation, since fluid medium is lost from the newly formed gel.

D. Structure

The rigidity of a gel arises from the presence of a network formed by the interlinking of particles gelling agent. The nature of the particles and the type of force that is responsible for the linkages, which determines the structure of the network and the properties of gel. The individual particles of hydrophilic colloid may consist of either spherical or an isometric aggregates of small molecules, or single macromolecules.

E. Rheology

Solutions of the gelling agents and dispersion of flocculated solid are pseudo plastic i.e.

exhibiting Non-Newtonian flow behaviour, characterized by a decrease in viscosity with increase in shear rate. The tenuous structure of inorganic particles dispersed in water is disrupted by n gels, ageing results in gradual formation of a denser network of the gelling agent.

1.4. Psoriasis^[6,7,8]

Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory disease predominantly affecting the skin and is estimated to occur in 2-3% of the population. A subset of these psoriasis patients will also develop psoriatic arthritis, a seronegative spondyloarthropathy. In psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis, a dysregulation of multiple pro- inflammatory and anti-inflammatory mediators occurs in dendritic cells, monocytes, macrophages, neutrophils, T cells, B cells, keratinocytes, chondrocytes, and synoviocytes. The cascade of aberrant immune signaling, triggered by stress, physical injury, drugs, or infection, is believed to underlie the clinical signs of inflammation, pain, and pruritus, as well as the histological signs such as keratinocyte hyper proliferation, scaling, and in subsets of patients, pustular or guttate plaques and nail and joint involvement. Because of the chronic nature of psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis, long term treatment is often required. Systemic therapies are typically recommended for patients with moderate psoriasis affecting 3-10% of the body surface area, and for severe psoriasis affecting more than 10% of the body surface area, or for patients who experience significant psoriasis-related impairments in quality of life. Research efforts continue in effective in the treatment of psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis.

1.3.1 Pathophysiology of psoriasis and dermatologic inflammation

Acute inflammatory reactions typically occur in response to infection and are coupled with the release of local factors that prevent excessive trafficking of leukocytes, allowing for resolution of inflammation. Resolution of an acute inflammatory response within the local tissues and a re-establishment of immunological homeostasis are necessary for ongoing health. Skin is an important site for antigen presentation, and epidermal Langerhans cells and dermal dendritic cells play pivotal roles in T cell- mediated immune response to antigens encounters in skin. Regulatory feedback loops help to balance pro- inflammatory signaling pathways and anti-inflammatory signaling pathways, maintaining the homeostatic functioning of the skin immune system.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

2 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

2.1. AIM: The aim of the present work is to formulate Topical Gel of Antipsoriatic Drug and Evaluate for its Invitro Performance.

2.2. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of present study are:

- To increase the solubility and permeability of the drug.
- To Prepare and Optimize the formula of Gel.
- To screen the different components for the preparation of gel.
- To evaluate the prepared and optimized gel for Description, pH, Viscosity, Assay, In-vitro Diffusion study, Stability study.

Literature Review

Deepa Singh (2023)

Determined Anti-Psoriatic Activity of Salicylic Acid and Wrightia Tinctoria Herb Using Extemporaneous Formulation. This study was conducted to develop and evaluation of gel and beads formulations i.e. extemporaneous formulation for psoriasis by using Carbopol 934 as a gelling agent. The gel formulations were evaluated for physical appearance, drug release and stability. The drug release from carbopol 934 as a gelling agent through a standard cellophane membrane was evaluated using Franz-Diffusion Cell. The gel formulation showed acceptable physical properties concerning color, homogeneity, consistency, spreadability and pH value as well as beads also showed good results with suitable size and no foreign matter is observed. The drug release by polymer Carbopol 934 show high concentration release and Stability studies showed that the formulation remained unchanged upon storage for six months at ambient conditions.

Zehui Chen (2015)

The main objective of this study was to Formulate and evaluate topical liposomal gel containing a combination of zedoary turmeric oil and tretinoin for psoriasis activity This study was to develop a combination of zedoary turmeric oil (ZTO) and tretinoin (TRE)-loaded liposomal gel as a topical drug delivery system. The optimized liposome vesicles were incorporated into Carbopol gel matrix and studied by continuous *in vitro* (skin penetration and retention) and *in vivo* (anti-psoriatic activity using mouse model and mouse tail model)

experiments. Transmission electron microscopy showed liposomes had a regular spherical surface. After 1 month storage at $(4 \pm 2) ^\circ\text{C}$, the optimized liposome preparations maintained its stability. *In vitro* study indicated that liposome formulations could significantly prolong the penetration of drugs into the hair follicles of mice and keep more drugs in the skin compared with conventional gel formulations. *In vivo* study showed that liposomal gel was more effective than conventional gel in treating psoriasis and had a significant dose-dependent effect on psoriasis. In summary, liposomal gel is expected to be an ideal carrier for topical drug delivery systems of ZTO and TRE.

Md. Sarfaraz Alam (2010)

Designed and evaluate for its Characterization of Nanostructure Topical Gel of Betamethasone Dipropionate for Psoriasis The aim of this study was to investigate and evaluate a nanoemulsion topical gel of betamethasone dipropionate. For the preparation of nanoemulsion eucalyptus oil and babchi oil was taken. Nanomulsions were prepared by aqueous phase-titration method. Pseudoternary phase diagrams were constructed for the identification of nanoemulsion existence zones. Prepared nanoemulsions were subjected to different thermodynamic stability tests and characterized for droplet size, viscosity and refractive index. *In vitro* skin permeation of betamethasone dipropionate through rat abdominal skin was determined by the Franz diffusion cell. The prepared nanoemulsion gel is a potential vehicle for improved topical delivery of BD for better treatment of psoriasis.

Farah Khan (2020)

In this article it was studied that Antipsoriatic and Antieczematic Activity of Polyherbal Developed Gel on Swiss Albino Mice. Developed gel (4.5% w/w Carbapol 934) Swiss albino mice give relevant result for treatment of psoriasis, without any tissue toxicity such as redness, erythematic in animal skin, as well as convulsion, tremor, circling, depression, hypothermia and mortality. Percent drug activity of Developed gel (4.5% w/w Carbapol 934) was found to be 19.37 % which show a significant antipsoriatic effect in comparison of standard drug Derobin® (1.125w/w) 12.90 %. Developed polyherbal gel is more effective as compared to standard drug Derobin®.

Sonia Tomar (2024)

Formulation and Evaluation of Topical Gel Containing Azithromycin and Prednisolone Vesicles for Treating Psoriasis Preparation and evaluate Topical Gel by varying concentration of corbopol in their formulation and checked its effect on release and evaluate its invitro

performance.

P. Srinivasa Babu (2023)

Formulation and evaluation of antipsoriatic gel using natural excipients formulations of Psoralen using natural excipients to minimize the side effects of synthetic drugs. The Psoralen gel formulations were prepared using different natural gums and polymers. The physicochemical compatibility between Psoralen and other excipients was confirmed by using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. All prepared gel formulations were evaluated for drug content uniformity, viscosity, pH, and stability. The release of psoralen from all formulations using dialysis membrane into a phosphate buffer pH 6.8 at 37°C was studied. Drug release from the formulations fitted best to the Higuchi model. From the drug release data the best formulation was optimized and the biological studies on albino mice were performed.

Kamlesh Wadher (2019)

Herbal gel was prepared containing *Pongamia pinnata* extracts using Carbopol 934 as gelling agent. The prepared gel formulations were studied for pH, viscosity, Spreadability and in vitro diffusion studies. The imiquimod-induced psoriatic mouse model, showed a prominent anti-psoriatic activity of the extract evident through index grading. Treatment with extract confirmed a noteworthy reduction in psoriasis in the treated groups as there was a considerable diminution in the thickness and scaling of skin.

Ravi (2010)

In that study, gels with carbopol, HPMC K4M, MC, HPC were prepared with different permeation enhancers like, MSO, lemongrass oil, menthe oil, oleic acid. They were evaluated for physicochemical properties, drug release. After in-vitro evaluation of gel formulations, ex-vivo permeation of etoricoxib was evaluated across rat epidermis and human cadaver skin. The best formulation was then evaluated for the anti-inflammatory and skin irritation study.

Jadhav A. J. (2014)

Formulated and evaluated of pH dependent zolmitriptan insitu. They used the mixture of carbopol 940 and HPMC D100 was used to confer pH sensitive gelation property. They evaluated for parameters like pH, drug content, viscosity, mucoadhesive strength, gel strength, in vitro drug release, in vitro permeation and drug excipients compatibility. The results showed that formulation containing 0.1% of carbopol 940 and 0.2% HPMC K100 was found to have desirable results.

Venkat Vardhan Reddy K. (2014)

Developed immediate release liquid fill formulations for soft gels of sumatriptan succinate. They prepared formulations using excipients like PEG 400, PG, PVP K-30, SLS, antioxidants, Tween-80, ethanol and purified water. They evaluated the parameters of appearance, pH, drug content uniformity, drug-excipients compatibility, viscosity and stability in *in vitro* dissolution studies. The results revealed that *in vitro* dissolution properties of SMT liquid fill formulations or soft gels were superior when compared to the pure SMT and marketed SMT

Samuel T. Hwang (2016)

In this article recent advances in the immunology, epidemiology, and genetics/genomics of psoriasis were explained. Advances sometimes generate more questions, and this article makes an attempt to point out where controversies might exist in the literature. Many of the articles mentioned were published in the Journal of Investigative Dermatology, but many articles from the broader scientific literature are also cited, to provide context and to add further validity for some of these key findings. Among the themes we explore are the identification of antigens in psoriasis, the co-morbidities of psoriasis, and novel integrative approaches to genome-wide association studies.

Saba A. Jaber (2018)

Topical semisolid FLB preparations were formulated using different semisolid formulation starting from emulsion bases w/o and o/w comparing with different gelling agents in different concentrations which include carbopol 934, sodium carboxy methylcellulose (SCMC) and combination of both polymer in different concentration to get 1% gelling agents. All the gel formulations were evaluated for physical appearance, pH, spreadability, rheological studies, drug content, *in vitro* release and diffusion studies. Results: All gel formulations which contain gelling agent exhibit better *in vitro* drug release and permeation compared with the emulsion bases, especially 1% polymer combination. Ethanol exerts a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) on the *in vitro* drug release and diffusion for 2% carbopol 934 compared with SCMC. Drug content was found to be uniform in all the formulations. The pH ranges of formulated gels were found to be suitable for topical application

Materials And Equipments

The below listed materials and equipments/Instruments are used in formulation of topical gel.

Drug and Excipient Profile

2.3. Drug Profile

2.3.1. Apremilast

- Apremilast is a novel, orally available phosphodiesterase (PDE-4) inhibitor. It is indicated for the treatment of certain types of psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis. It may also be useful for other immune system related inflammatory diseases.
- Structure

Figure 5: Structure of Apremilast.

- **Category:** Antirheumatic agent, Antipsoriatic agent and immunomodulating agent.
- **Description:** Apremilast is Yellow to white powder
- **BCS class:** Class IV
- **Molecular weight:** 460.500 g/mol
- **Solubility:** Aqueous solubility – 225.4 mg/L
- **Partition coefficient:** -0.45
- **Melting point:** 156°C
- **Half-life:** 6-9 hours
- **Bioavailability:** 73%
- **Protein binding:** 68%
- **Volume of distribution:** Peak plasma concentration (C_{max}) occur at a median time (t_{max}) of ~2.5 hours

It is metabolized in the liver, mainly via the enzyme CYP3A4, but to a minor extent via CYP1A2 and CYP2A6.

➤ Mechanism

PDE-4 is a cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP)-specific phosphodiesterase that is predominantly located in inflammatory cells. By inhibiting PDE-4, Apremilast increases intracellular levels of cAMP and thereby inhibits the production of multiple proinflammatory

mediators including PDE-4, TNF- α , interleukin-2 (IL-2), interferon- γ , leukotrienes, and nitric oxide synthase. By targeting a central component of the inflammatory signaling cascade rather than a single inflammatory marker, PDE-4 inhibition may restore the homeostatic balance between pro- and anti-inflammatory signaling.

➤ Toxicity

Depression and suicide: Apremilast has been associated with increased depression and suicidal behavior in patients. Weight loss: Apremilast has been associated with weight decrease in patients.

1. FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT

1.1. PURPOSE OF FORMULATION

Existing medication for Psoriasis, Apremilast oral dosage forms are available. So there is no other dosage forms for Apremilast. But oral dosage forms can lead to many severe side effects like Gastrointestinal irritation, tolerability like nausea, vomiting due to first pass metabolism of drug. Topical agent can bring localized action and first pass metabolism also be avoided. Gels are having rapid onset of action and high rate of absorption. Hence, the topical gel preparation for Apremilast was selected. Approximately 80% of psoriasis patients have mild to moderate diseases that can be treated with Apremilast oral route.

1.2. DESIGNING THE FORMULA

Carbopol ultrez 10 NF concentration in Apremilast topical gel range from 1-1.2% and Dimethyl sulfoxide concentration range from 10-15%, Propylene glycol concentration range from 22.3- 29.3%, Glycerine concentration range from 24.3-29.3%, Ethanol concentration range from 5-6%. Hence ideal range of Carbopol ultrez 10 NF 1.2%, Dimethyl sulfoxide 10%, Propylene glycol 29.3%, Glycerine 24.30%, Ethanol USP 6% were selected for the formulation of Apremilast topical gel.

1.3. JUSTIFICATION

Topical gels recently have acquired great importance in the pharmaceutical field due to their unique properties such as Gels often provide a faster release of drug substance, rapid onset of action, and bypass first pass metabolism of drug. This gel provides an advantage of psoriatic patients. Psoriasis is a chronic, immune-mediated, inflammatory disease characterized by distinctive, red raised skin lesions with adherent silvery scales. Psoriasis is a lifelong recurrent disease that often requires ongoing treatment to reduce disease symptoms, improve

quality of life and maintain remission. This is a serious medical condition has become a major public health issue and its prevalence is rapidly increasing among the population.

The development of topically available small molecules that regulate the production of inflammatory mediators within the psoriasis signaling pathway may address unmet needs for patients who are intolerant of conventional non biologic therapies or who are not candidates for biologic treatments. Combined treatments with topical therapies are common clinical practice to control the disease and to reduce the total risk of the systemic agent thereby, at least theoretically lessen risk of serious adverse effects.

1.4. PREFORMULATION STUDIES:

Preformulation studies can be defined as an investigation of physical and chemical properties of new drug substance alone or in combination with other excipients. It is a phase of research and development process, carried out in order to develop a stable, safe and effective dosage form. These are also used for the determination of suitable excipients for the fabrication of dosage forms. Preformulation studies include solubility studies, construction of standard graph and drug- polymer compatibility studies using FT-IR.

1.4.1. Determination of API solubility in different solvents

Aprimilast is a BCS Class IV drug [Low solubility and Low permeability], so solubility study were conducted to determine its highest solubility.

Solubility of Aprimilast were checked in various solvents i.e. Ethanol, Transcutol P, Glycerol, Propylene Glycol, DMSO, Castor Oil, Mineral Oil, Peceol, etc.

Amongst all solvents the highest solubility of Aprimilast was obtained in Dimethyl Sulphoxide (DMSO), so it is used as solvent and also it is used as permeation enhancer.

Ethanol, Propylene Glycol and Glycerol can be used as cosolvents.

1.4.2. Drug-polymer compatibility studies FT-IR spectroscopy

Study of the compatibility between the drug and the excipients is an important process in the development of a stable solid dosage form. Drug excipients compatibility testing at an early stage helps in the selection of excipients that increases the probability of developing a stable dosage form. Incompatibility between drug and excipient can alter stability and bioavailability of drugs, affecting its safety and efficacy.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) is a simple technique for the detection of changes with excipients-drug mixture. Disappearance of an absorption peak or reduction of the peak intensity combined with the appearance of new peaks gives a clear evidence for interactions between drug and excipients. For the FT-IR studies of our samples the sample was grounded gently with anhydrous KBr and compressed to form pellet. The scanning range was 400-4000 cm^{-1} .

1.4.3. Standard calibration curve

Calibration curve of Aprimilast in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer

Preparation of buffer

Solution of phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 was prepared by taking 6.8043 g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate and 1.5638 g of sodium hydroxide and dissolving them in sufficient amount of water. The volume was then made up to 1000 ml with distilled water.

Preparation of stock

- 100 mg of drug was weighed and transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask. 50 mL of Ph 7.4 phosphate buffer and sonicated to dissolve, then made up to 100 mL with pH 7.4 phosphate buffer and named as Stock I.
- From Stock I 10 mL of solution was taken and made up to 100 mL pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. This was named as Stock II.
- From this 1 mL, 2 mL, 3 mL, 4 mL and 5 mL solution was taken made up to 10 mL with buffer to obtain 10 μg , 20 μg , 30 μg , 40 μg and 50 μg concentrations respectively.
- The absorbance was noted at 263 nm in UV spectrophotometer.

A calibration curve was constructed by plotting the absorbance against the concentration of Aprimilast. A regression equation was derived from the plot, which was used for the estimation of Aprimilast against pH 7.4 PBS.

- The method obeyed Beer's law in the concentration range of 10-50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and is suitable for the estimation of Aprimilast from different sample solutions. The correlation coefficient value (r) was found to be 0.998 indicating a positive correlation between the concentration of Aprimilast and the corresponding absorbance values. The regression line describing the relation between concentration and absorbance was as follows:

$$y = 0.0849 x + 0.0541$$

Where,

y is the absorbance at 263 nm and

x is the concentration of Aprimilast in $\mu\text{g/ml}$

1.5. Preparation of Aprimilast Topical Gel

1.5.1. Aprimilast topical gel was prepared by the following method.

1. Purified water, glycerine and propylene glycols were mixed together.
2. Carbopol 10NF dispersed uniformly in the above mixture under stirring for 2 hrs.
3. Aprimilast was dissolved in DMSO and is added to carbopol dispersion under stirring.
4. Methyl and propyl parabens were dissolved in absolute ethanol and is added to above mixture. Continue the stirring for 30min.
5. pH of the gel was adjusted with 10% w/w NaOH solution.

1.5.2. Manufacturing Formula

Table 4: Formulae of different formulations (For 100 g).

Formulation	F1	F2	F3	F4
Ingredient	mg/100g	mg/100g	mg/100g	mg/100g
Aprimilast	2.0	2.0	4.0	4.0
DMSO	10.0	15.0	15.0	10.0
Carbopol 10NF	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
Propylene glycol	27.3	24.3	24.3	24.3
Glycerine	28.3	26.3	24.3	29.3
Ethanol	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
Methyl paraben	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Propyl paraben	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Purified water	25.0	25.0	25.0	25.0

1.6. Evaluation

1. Description

All the developed hydrophilic gels were examined physically for colour, appearance and consistency.

2. pH measurement

pH of the gels were measured using digital pH meter. 10%w/w of the gel was prepared by dispersing 1g of gel in purified water and pH was measured using digital pH meter.

3. Assay (% w/w)

The assay for formulations was checked for all the formulations, the assay of formulation should be in between 98% to 102%.

4. Rheological determination (Viscosity)

Viscosities of the prepared gels were measured using cone and plate viscometer with spindle no. 1 at $25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. About 0.1mg of the gel to be tested was placed on the plate and spindle was allowed to rotate at different RPMs. The viscosity was determined at different values of the shearrate and all the measurement were made in duplicate.

5. In Vitro Drug Diffusion Studies^[10,12,13]

The *in vitro* drug release studies were carried out using a modified vertical Franz diffusion cell (with effective diffusion area 4.9 cm² and 14 ml cell volume). The formulation was applied on Strat M membrane 0.45 μm which was sandwiched between donor and receptor compartment of the franz diffusion cell. Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 + methanol (80:20) was used as a diffusion media. The temperature of the cell was maintained at 37 ± 0.2 OC by kept it in water bath. This whole assembly was kept on amagnetic stirrer and the solution was stirred continuously using a magnetic bead at 600 rpm. The samples (1.0 ml aliquots) were withdrawn at suitable time interval and analysed for drug content by HPLC spectrophotometer at 240 nm after appropriate dilutions.

6. Stability studies

The optimised gel was packed in laminated tubes and loaded for stability at 40C/75%RH and 30C/65%RH for 1, 2 and 3 months. At regular time intervals the samples were withdrawn and evaluated for appearance pH, rheological behaviour (viscosity), assay and in vitro drug diffusion studies.

2. RESULT

2.1. CALIBRATION CURVE

Table 5: Calibration curve for the estimation of Aprimilast (in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer).

Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	Absorbance
10	0.2216 ± 0.0011
20	0.3979 ± 0.0020
30	0.5593 ± 0.0015
40	0.736 ± 0.001
50	0.9011 ± 0.0045
Intercept	0.0541
Slope	0.0849
Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.9986

All the values are expressed as mean \pm SD (n=3)

Figure 13: Calibration curve of Aprimilast.

2.2. IR Analysis

Figure14: FT-IR of Drug Aprimilast.

Figure 15: FTIR of Aprimalst and Ethanol.

Figure 16: FT-IR of Aprimilast and Carbopol.

Figure 17: FT-IR of Aprimilast and Dimethyl Sulphoxide.

Figure 18: FT-IR of Aprimilast and Propylene Glycol.

Figure 19: FT-IR of Aprimilast and Glycerol.

Figure 20: FT-IR of physical mixture.

7.3. Evaluation of Formulated Aprimilast Topical Gels

Table 6: Physical properties for Aprimilast topical gels (F1 – F4).

Formulations→	F1	F2	F3	F4
Test parameters↓				
Description	White to off white viscous gel			
pH	4.84	4.92	4.99	4.88
Assay (% w/w)	101.2	100.5	100.9	101.1
Viscosity (cps)	3654	3701	4078	3800

7.4. In vitro drug diffusion study for the formulations (F1 – F4)

Table 7: In vitro drug diffusion profiles of formulations (F1 – F4).

Time (Hrs)	Formulation codes and respective drug release profiles (%) of Aprimilast topical gel			
	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0
8	14.7 ±0.5	18.7 ±0.5	19.1 ±0.5	15.2 ±0.7
12	19.8 ±0.9	21.0 ±0.3	24.0 ±0.9	23.5 ±0.8
24	75.2 ±0.7	59.2 ±0.5	69.9 ±0.7	60.4 ±0.9
30	81.5 ±0.8	85.2 ±0.9	96.4 ±0.8	85.2 ±0.8
48	89.5 ±0.8	91.2 ±0.6	98.2 ±0.6	94.2 ±0.6

Figure 21: In-vitro drug diffusion profiles for formulations (F1 – F4).

Figure 22: FT-IR of Optimized formulation (F3).

7.5. Stability studies for the formulation

Optimized formulation (F3) loaded for stability at accelerated condition (40°C/75%RH) and evaluate parameters shown in Table No.8.

Table 8: Physical parameters for Stability loaded formulations at condition (40°C/75%RH) (F3).

Condition→ Parameter↓	Initial/RT	1 Month	2 Month	3 Month
Description	White to off white viscous gel	White to offwhite viscous gel	White to off white viscous gel	White to off white viscous gel
pH	4.84	4.97	4.86	4.98
Assay (%)	100.9	100.5	100.1	100.0
Viscosity (cps)	4078	3891	3765	3689

Optimized Formulation (F3) was loaded for stability at condition 30°C/65%RH and evaluate its parameters shown in Table No.9.

Table 9: Physical parameters for Stability loaded formulations at condition 30°C/65% (F3).

Condition→ Parameter↓	Initial/RT	1 Month	2 Month	3 Month
Description	White to off white viscous gel	White to off-white viscous gel	White to off white viscous gel	White to off white viscous gel
pH	4.84	4.92	4.95	4.98
Assay (%)	100.9	100.8	100.5	100.2
Viscosity (cps)	4078	3910	3865	3690

7.6. In Vitro Drug Diffusion study of Optimized formulation

Table 10: In vitro drug diffusion data for stability loaded formulations (F3).

Condition→ Time point↓	40°C/75%RH			30°C/65%RH		
	1 month	2 month	3 month	1 month	2 month	3 month
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	17.2	17.1	16.8	18.2	18.5	17.8
12	22.9	23.2	22.9	25.4	24.6	23.8
24	65.8	65.1	63.8	71.2	69.5	69.7
30	92.5	93.5	94.5	94.2	93.7	93.2
48	98.2	98.0	96.2	97.2	97.4	96.7

Figure 23: In vitro drug diffusion profiles for stability loaded formulations (F3) at condition 40°C/75%RH.

Figure 24: In vitro drug diffusion profiles for stability loaded formulations (F3) at condition 30°C/65%RH

7.1.1 Preformulation Studies

7.1.2 Fourier Transfer Infrared Spectrophotometry (FT-IR)

Infrared spectra for pure drug, excipients, physical mixture and Optimized topical gel of Aprimilast were determined to find the compatibility of the drug in the mixture using FTIR-Spectrophotometer by disc method. The FTIR were performed and the spectra obtained are represented from **Figure 14 to Figure 20, Figure 22**.

The FT-IR results showed that the prominent characteristic peaks of the drugs are maintained in the physical mixtures as well as in the final formulations which is an indication that there are no interactions affecting the activity of the drug. These excipients could be used for further study using these combinations.

7.1.3 Construction of calibration curve

Calibration curve for Aprimilast using pH 7.4 phosphate buffer

The calibration curve was constructed by preparing 10 µg/ml, 20 µg/ml, 30 µg/ml, 40 µg/ml and 50 µg/ml concentrations as the serial dilutions and then finding the corresponding absorbance values spectrophotometrically at 240nm. The data is represented in **Table 05**. The slope and intercept values were found to be 0.0849 and 0.0541 respectively and the correlation coefficient was 0.9986.

The calibration curve is represented in **Figure 13**. From the slope and intercept values it is observed that the curve is having a positive slope and positive intercept. The coefficient of correlation value of 0.9986 is satisfactory. From the data it is evident that the concentration range from 10 µg/mL to 50 µg/mL is within the linearity range as per the Beer's Lambert's law.

7.2 Preparation of Aprimilast Topical Gel

The Aprimilast Topical Gels were prepared as per the desired method. The formulae for the four formulations are tabulated in **Table 4**. And the manufacturing process are shown in **Figure 12**.

7.3 Evaluation studies of Aprimilast Topical Gel

7.3.1 Description

The formulated gels were physically examined for the colour, appearance and consistency, the results were found satisfactory for all the four formulations (F1-F4).

7.3.2 pH measurement

pH for all the formulation were tested using pH meter, among the four formulations F3 showed pH **4.99**.

7.3.3 Assay (% w/w)

The assay for formulations was checked, among all the four formulations, the assay value for F3 formulation was **100.9 %w/w**.

7.3.4 Viscosity (cps)

The viscosity for the formulations were measured using cone and plate viscometer, for F3 formulation the viscosity was **4078 cps**, which showed the best consistency among all the four formulations.

7.3.5 In vitro drug diffusion study

The release of Aprimilast from the topical gels was carried out.

Overall, the four formulations (F1- F4), the F3 showed the highest percentage of drug release **98.2%** for 48 hours

8.2.SUMMARY

- FTIR spectroscopy studies confirmed that there is compatibility between drug and excipients.
- Gel was prepared by using Dimethyl sulfoxide, Carbopol 10NF, propylene glycol, glycerol, methyl paraben, propyl paraben and water.
- The Optimized formulation (F3) is more effective compared to all formulations.
- The Prepared Gel showed acceptable Physical properties such as pH (4.99), assay (100.9%w/w) And In vitro diffusion studies have shown 98.2% drug release in 48 hours.
- Formulation was loaded for stability at Accelerated condition 40°C/75%RH and 30°C/65%RH for 1,2 and 3 month. Optimized formulation (F3) has shown good stability and acceptable In vitro performance.

8.3.CONCLUSION

- Aprimilast is a BCS class IV drug it's having low solubility as well as low permeability and it is used for antipsoriatic activity.
- By using cosolvents and permeation enhancer we can enhance its solubility and permeability through the skin.
- All the result shows it is having good In vitro drug release and permeation which studied by using Franz diffusion cell.
- For future studies work will be continued to check the anti-psoriasis effect of Aprimilast using animal model.

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